

EXPLORERS

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University of Iowa

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

ece.engineering.uiowa.edu

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The **University of Iowa** is one of the nation's premier public research universities with 32,535 students from 114 countries and all 50 states with 11 graduate programs ranked among the top 10 in the country.

At the University of Iowa **Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering**, research programs and classroom instruction are headed by an outstanding faculty. We are proud to have among our faculty a National Science Foundation Presidential Faculty Fellow, a National Science Foundation National Young Investigator, and several Fellows of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers and the Optical Society of America, and a Fellow of the American Institute for Medical and Biological Engineering.

Available facilities support interdisciplinary research and include individual laboratories as well as access to specialized facilities of the Optical Science and Technology Center, Center for Computer Aided Design, Iowa Driving Simulator, Iowa Institute for Hydraulics Research, and Iowa Institute for Biomedical Imaging.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x3 CHALLENGES

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Environment
Transport
Disasters

CHALLENGE #13 - UI-AUG-01

→ Augmented Reality-Based Flood Visualizer

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Increasing disaster awareness is one of the main strategies to mitigate disaster damages. Allowing public to visualize a flood event at their location is a striking way to convey the potential effects. While developing this application, the developer may benefit from the available tools for AR such as Apple AR Kit. The development can be done for either or both Android and iPhone.

OBJECTIVES

- Develop a mobile application with capabilities of creating an AR layer for flood visualization
- Deploy realistic water simulation tools and asset

SKILLS REQUIRED

- Self-learning and research capabilities
- Mobile Development Experience (either Android or iOS)
- VR/AR understanding and experience
- Any experience on visualization and graphic design is a plus.

CHALLENGE #14 - UI-FLO-02

→ Detection and Generating Flood Images Using Satellite Imagery and Deep Neural Networks

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

CNN based image-to-image neural networks are employed in various fields and they show great potential. This project aims to research in the field and develop (a) an image-to-image neural network, either supervised or unsupervised, that converts regular satellite imagery of urban or suburban areas to images where a flood event occurred, (b) detect flooded area from satellite imagery. The aim is to understand how floods would affect various locations.

OBJECTIVES

The goal of this challenge is to develop (a) an image-to-image neural network to generate new versions of satellite imagery as if a flooding event occurred in the places pictured on the input satellite imagery, (b) detect flooded area from satellite imagery.

SKILLS REQUIRED

- Deep Learning
- Convolutional Neural Networks
- Python
- PyTorch or TensorFlow

CHALLENGE #15 - UI-LED-03

→ A Distributed Ledger using Blockchain for Water Monitoring Sensors

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Availability and sharing of water data can be difficult due to the needs of different organizations, cities, and countries. A reliable and trusted medium is needed to assure correct information is available to stakeholders in a timely manner.

OBJECTIVES

Design and develop a blockchain-based web application for organizations to record and share sensor readings for water resources monitoring.

SKILLS REQUIRED

- Blockchain development
- Dapp development
- Web technologies (HTML, JS, CSS)

